

THE EXPRESSION OF EDUCATIONAL AND MORAL VIEWS IN THE WORKS OF ABDURRAHMAN JAMI

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Abstract

In this article, like thinkers who lived in the 15th century, he extensively illuminated ideas about ensuring human happiness through the glorification of man and his high moral qualities and beautiful qualities.

Keywords: thinker, virtue, happiness, scholar, madrasah, teacher.

The scholar's full name is Nuriddin Abdurrahman ibn Ahmad, who was born on November 7, 1414 in the city of Jam. After graduating from school, Abdurahman Jami continued his education at the Nizamiya madrasah. During his studies at the madrasa, he thoroughly studied the grammar of the Arabic language, as well as familiarized himself with the content of works created in Arabic and teaching the science of aruz and its specific aspects.

He was privileged to get acquainted with the commentaries of many works of art. At the same time, he studied under scholars such as Sa'diddin Kashgari, Sheikh Bahovuddin Umar, and Mawlana Muhammad Asad. Abdurrahman Jami received praise from his teachers for his thorough mastery of the sciences of creating works of art and his ability to successfully create prose and poetic works. During his stay in Samarkand, Abdurrahman Jami was able to listen to the lectures delivered by the outstanding scholar of his time, Kazizade Rumi. After returning to Herat, he was tested by Ali Kushchi, one of the favorite students of the famous scientist, Muhammad Taragay Ulugh Beg.

There was a strong friendly relationship between Alisher Navoi and Jami, the ruler of the kingdom of scholarship and poetry, and this relationship was clearly visible in the field of both artistic creativity, everyday life, and social relations.

Renowned orientalists who conducted research on the life and creative work of Abdurrahman Jami, his educational and upbringing views, such as M. Orifi, A. Kayumov, Sh. Shamukhamedov, K. Alikulov, and E.E. Bertels.

Jami gained a worthy place in the development of world culture with his three lyrical divans, "Haft Aurang" (Seven Throne), and educational works "Bahoristan," consisting of seven dastans. The number of all his works was determined by researchers as 46 (A. Kayumov).

In his work "Bahoristan," Abdurrahman Jami outlines all the criteria for human perfection. The scholar also emphasizes that in the upbringing of a person as an individual, alongside material factors, the role of spiritual factors is incomparable. Overall, in Jami's works, spiritual and moral qualities related to the upbringing of a mature person are expressed in a comprehensive way, which are of great importance for the implementation of the upbringing of a perfect person, which is the main goal of our modern society.

Educational work, high moral concepts (which are closely related to the idea of education and patriotism); Violence, discord, greed, envy, indifference, In conclusion, it should be said that insult, shame, slander, enmity, greed, dishonesty, ignorance, anger, betrayal, etc. are interpreted. The author briefly, clearly and concisely explains their place and role in human life and destiny. This deepening of morality is undoubtedly important for today's youth. The spirit of national awakening in the peoples of Turkestan at the beginning of the 20th century is reflected in the works of Abdurakhman Jami, in a number of ideas and ideas. In particular, caring for the future of the nation, thinking about the future of the homeland, the need to pay primary attention to the upbringing of young people loyal to the people and the country, patriotism occupies a special place in the author's ideological and artistic content.

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